

Call for Papers

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Special Issue on [Internet of Things and Machine Learning in Smart Agriculture](#)

In the near future, the agricultural sector is called upon to face a significant challenge due to increasingly scarce resources, extreme weather conditions, population growth, and the reduction of cultivable land. One solution is to transition from the old concept of agriculture to Smart Agriculture, with the adoption of the Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning (ML). Despite the investments made in recent years to connect rural areas to the Internet, a barrier to the digitization of agriculture is represented by limited connectivity in peripheral areas. Scenario-specific IoT solutions are essential for easily connecting sensors/actuators over large rural areas and enabling new modes of interaction between the real world and the digital world.

This special issue (SI) invites research papers that propose innovative IoT solutions for data collection and processing directly in the field, at the edge of the network, supporting applications that rationalize the natural resources employed, reduce pollution, and optimize agricultural production, also powered by artificial intelligence particularly highlighting the integration of processing storage communications and sensing that is characterizing the development of the future infrastructures. Moreover, the SI focus extends to ML techniques for processing data at the edge or in a serverless manner and develop decision support systems that minimize traffic generated towards the Internet as well as the costs and energy consumption of the devices used for monitoring and controlling farms. The deployment of IoT and ML technologies in agriculture presents challenges. These include issues related to devices and sensors for Smart Agriculture, wireless communication network design, Edge-ML, heterogeneous data and sensors, data security, and the energy efficiency of the IoT device. Addressing these challenges requires significant research and development efforts. The scope of this Special Issue includes, but is not limited to, the following topics:

- Wireless sensing applications and technologies for smart agriculture
- Deployment and energy efficiency of IoT devices in smart farming
- The energy efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of wireless networks in rural areas
- Wireless communication for wearable plant sensors
- Energy autonomous and battery-free wireless sensors and their applications in smart agriculture
- Anomaly detection techniques and their application in agriculture and forestry
- Machine learning applications in agriculture for data processing at the edge or in serverless manner
- Scalability and interoperability of wireless networks for agriculture and forestry
- Dataset creation and usage of synthetic data for Edge-computing in agriculture
- Case studies highlighting the implementation of smart irrigation and farming
- Advantages of merging IoT sensors with ML in agriculture
- Internet of drones for smart agriculture and Edge-computing for image processing
- Digital Twin ecosystems and applications in agriculture

Manuscript submission information:

Manuscripts must be submitted via the Internet of Things online submission system ([Editorial Manager®](#)). Please select the article type “**VSI: Smart Agriculture**” when submitting your manuscript online.

Guest Editors:

Antonino Pagano, University of Palermo and CNIT, Italy (antonino.pagano@unipa.it)

Ilenia Tinnirello, University of Palermo, CNIT and University of Catania, Italy

Stefano Giordano, University of Pisa and CNIT, Italy

Giacomo Morabito, University of Catania and CNIT, Italy

Important Dates:

- Submission Open Date: **March 1, 2025**
- Final Submission Deadline: **May 1, 2026**
- Editorial Acceptance Deadline: **August 1, 2026**